

THE IMPORTANCE OF SPORTS CLUBS IN EDUCATING THE YOUNG GENERATION TO BE HEALTHY AND STABLE

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Abstract: The article examines the importance of sports clubs in improving students' vital skills and abilities, as well as their physical fitness.

Keywords: Physical education, sports clubs, event, goal, task, skills and abilities, healthy lifestyle, talented athletes, coach.

INTRODUCTION

Popularization of physical education and sports in our country is defined as one of the important directions of social policy. Because sport establishes a healthy way of life in the society by strengthening the health of the population, raising the young generation to be healthy and well-rounded. Attracting the young generation to regularly engage in physical education and sports, selecting, training and improving the skills of talented athletes in sports, training personnel, introducing modern technologies in the field and expanding international relations, strengthening the material and technical bases, and developing physical education and sports are among the main tasks.

The purpose of teaching features in the process of physical education and sports training is to teach pupils and students the requirements for physical development of the body and a healthy lifestyle. At the same time, physical training, sports and wellness events will greatly help to master professional training. Pupils and students' physical education activities are in the form of morning physical education, physical education classes, sports club training, sports fitness competitions and holidays. Morning physical education classes are held in public in student dormitories, independently in residence halls and families. The scientific work is one of the first to be done today. It analyzes the

importance of physical training and sports and health activities of pupils and students in raising the young generation as a well-rounded person.

The forms of improvement of this process are studied. The purpose of the research. By increasing the effectiveness of sports clubs in general education schools, it is necessary to determine the method of developing students' knowledge, skills and physical (strength, quickness, endurance, flexibility, agility) qualities.

TASKS OF THE RESEARCH

1. Study and analysis of scientific, theoretical, methodological sources on the subject, scientific justification of the relevance of problems.

2. Determination of physical fitness of students through Alpomish and Barchinoy special health tests

3. Scientific and pedagogical justification of the development of physical abilities of Umutalim school students.

METHODS OF RESEARCH ORGANIZATION

The correct organization of the research first of all depends on which method the researcher uses, because it is important for the researcher to be able to choose the time and participants of the research he is conducting correctly. Depending on the results of the exercises, and in which groups the growth rate is at its peak, the results of the groups with medium and low results will be compared, and other exercises will be selected accordingly.

Rule 1. Doing physical exercises in the morning. Rule 2. Eating right. Rule 3. Provide proper education to students. Rule 4. Correct selection of research groups, Research results and discussion. Physical education activities in educational institutions consist of physical development, health and preparation of pupils and students for life activities. Physical education processes are organized at all stages. In the organization of physical education, the pedagogical team of the educational institution, physical education teachers and sports coaches are of

great importance. Physical education activities in educational institutions are morning physical education, physical education classes, training in sports clubs, sports competitions and tourism activities conducted on holidays and weekends. In the physical education events, the students' movement skills and abilities are formed by performing vital activities such as walking, running, jumping, throwing, and climbing. Positive changes occur and the body becomes healthy with the help of physical exercises and the healing forces of nature, as well as hygienic means, which are considered as means of physical education.

The law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Public Education" and "On Physical Education and Sports" states that citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan must take care of their physical training in order to improve and strengthen their health. is keyed. This law fully applies to physical education in schools. Physical education of pupils and students is an organized pedagogical process of physical activity. Physical education activities in an educational institution differ in very diverse forms that require enthusiasm, initiative, and organization from pupils and students. They help to educate pupils and students in organizational skills, activity, resourcefulness.

PURPOSE OF STUDENTS' PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN AN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION:

1. Health.
2. Educate to become a mature person in every way.
3. Preparing for the defense of the Motherland and the cocktail.

Based on the purpose of physical education, the main tasks of physical education are defined in terms of health, exercise, physical development, formation of movement skills and abilities of pupils and students:

Giving special knowledge about physical exercises and sports, physical exercise is understood as a variety of voluntary movement activities that meet the requirements of the laws of physical education and are performed consciously.

Such movement activities have been historically systematized, collected and styled as gymnastics, games, sports, and tourism exercises. To instill in them hygienic knowledge and skills. This task is to give the pupil and student the necessary knowledge about the benefits of physical training, the hygienic rules and the rules for the correct performance of all physical exercises provided for in the program. All of these are directly related to health promotion, their knowledge and adherence to hygiene rules, which is achieved by the joint action of the school, family, community and children themselves. Exercise and sports are taught in physical education classes, daily activities, and club activities. As a result, physical development is ensured. Also, pupils and students are interested in sports and are attracted to sports. Strengthening health, helping students to develop and exercise properly. Under the influence of natural factors, water, sun, air, students' health will be strengthened, trained, and the body will be more resistant to diseases. Carrying out physical education activities in fresh air as much as possible or organizing sports halls with fresh air. Lead pupils and students in water treatments, swimming and bathing, and sunbathing activities. These activities are carried out in walks, excursions and tourism activities. This task is considered the most important of all physical culture and sports work in an educational institution. It should be the center of attention of every teacher and team of pedagogues. Therefore, pupils and students should have a normal physical development.

Formation and improvement of movement, skills and abilities, training in new movement types and movement activities. The content of the physical culture program of pupils and students is structured in such a way that students are regularly engaged in physical culture classes, at home, in physical culture clubs and sports clubs, and learn vital skills such as walking, running, throwing, crawling, and balancing. All the listed activities will help in all-round physical development, preparing them for cocktails. It is necessary to approach them

according to their gender, age, physical fitness and personal abilities in order to form movement skills and abilities of pupils and students. Speed, strength, agility and endurance and flexibility are qualities that everyone needs. They are inextricably linked with the formation of movement skills in pupils and students. Carrying out physical exercises for a short or long time at different speeds and with different complications helps to develop the above qualities. Development of physical qualities in accordance with each other. Organizing classes according to the personal abilities of the participants and involving students in sports. Education of mental and aesthetic qualities. Cultivating bravery, determination, discipline, community, sense of friendship and camaraderie, cultural behavior skills, attitude to work and social property. The whole process of physical education helps to cultivate such valuable moral and willful qualities. Many physical exercises, play activities help to cultivate the feelings of kindness and friendship. Also, formation and upbringing of love for the Motherland, patriotism, feelings.

Forming the right figure. Forming the skills of correct posture while standing and walking. Correct formation of the figure is a complex and long-lasting process. Therefore, in order to achieve positive results in this area, it is advisable to maintain a correct posture when standing and walking; physical exercises should be widely used; It is necessary to include in the content of physical culture classes exercises related to height improvement, pre-class gymnastics, physical culture times, physical education, pupils and students should constantly work on themselves with physical and mental exercises, and give homework . It is planned to achieve results on the basis of timely verification of given tasks and testing in practice. Educating pupils and students in a wide range of mental and moral aspects is one of the most important tasks, because the consciousness of pupils and students is during development. The desired results can be achieved only when education is directed in a positive direction. Involvement in physical

education and sports activities. It consists in accustoming pupils and students to systematic physical exercises not only in educational institutions, but also at home. In order to fulfill this important task, all activities conducted with pupils and students should be lively, the content and form of the studied material should be interesting, exciting, conducted under the sincere treatment of the leader of the activity, the participants should interact with each other. It is necessary to create conditions for cooperation. To attract pupils and students to engage in sports according to their personal interests and physical abilities. Also, it is necessary to carry out general physical training and sports activities in the places of residence, in sports circles. Education of organization in pupils and students, preparation of physical culture activities. In order to successfully carry out public physical culture and sports activities in the educational institution, to conduct physical culture classes and trainings in full, students and students need the constant support of the teacher of physical culture activities. Organizers of physical culture, team captains, group leaders in sports circles are elected among pupils and students. They are selected from among active participants. They closely support the physical culture team in the organization and management of physical education and sports events. Also, it is of great importance in attracting pupils and students to sports and increasing their interest in physical education.

Physical development is the emergence, change and improvement of biological forms and functions in the body under the influence of education. This process is subject to the laws of structure, change, quantity and quality of the organism and its living environment. Strengthening the human body from a physical point of view necessarily occurs in accordance with the physical loads given to the body and as a result of proper training. The process of teaching physical activity. Its task is to perform the behavior and improve it to ensure the emergence of the skill. This process is repeated many times until the completion of this stage. Each repetition looks the same on the outside, but the content of

each time is new inside. He will have received something different from the previous one. Figuratively speaking, "repetition - without repetition", "practice - without practice" is like repetition. It is in this way that the basis of the formation of the new movement activity is hidden. It is necessary to develop the spiritual qualities of the participants and connect them with life, society, and the needs of the work. It is necessary to encourage those engaged in the process of physical education to actively participate in the struggle to build a new society. How they live, what they think about, how they work in production, how they study at school, how they behave in the family, in public places, in order to educate employees in the spirit of the idea of national independence. Physical education specialists should know how to spend their time and others. It is necessary for physical education specialists to know the level of development of physical abilities of the participants, to study individual character traits, intelligence, perception, emotional will, moral qualities, and individual differences in static needs. In the process of independent training, pupils' and students' attitude to physical education and sports is formed, the skills of independent exercise, movement and sports are increased. Along with teaching vital movements in independent training, physical qualities such as strength, endurance, flexibility, quickness, and agility are improved. As a result of the development of each physical quality, changes occur in the body. The organs of the human body are strengthened and the blood circulation develops as a result of improvement.

DISCUSSION

All employees of the educational institution must understand the purpose, tasks, content and forms of physical education of pupils and students correctly, participate in practical work based on their activities, physical culture between pupils and parents. and actively promote sports. Physical education teachers must perform the following tasks:

- to ensure that the class is held at a high level and complete the physical

training program of the corresponding class;

- together with the doctor, conduct the medical examination of the students on time and take into account the results of the medical examination in their work;

- proper sanitation of the places where classes are held

- ensuring that it is kept in a hygienic condition;

- all pupils and students should be able to do physical exercises in comfortable clothes;

- participation in the organization and conduct of activities outside the educational institution on physical education and wide involvement of pupils and students in it;

- carrying out explanatory work between parents about the importance of physical education of pupils and students;

- regularly improving the knowledge of pupils and students in the field of physical education;

- to make pupils and students interested in physical culture and to form habits of regular exercise in them.

Teachers exchange experience to improve their skills, organize analysis of each other's lessons. The physical culture team performs the main tasks in the organization of physical training and sports events in educational institutions. Physical education teachers conduct physical education classes and daily physical education activities. Pupils who are active in physical education, and members and leaders of the youth society closely support physical education teachers in organizing physical education activities and sports competitions, holidays, excursions, excursions and tourism, and tourist marches.

At the same time, student athletes play an important role in attracting other students to sports and increasing their interest in physical education.

CONCLUSION

We have made a number of necessary concrete conclusions in our scientific

research and pedagogical practical work on the organization of physical training, sports and wellness activities with pupils and students in educational institutions.

1. In the processes of physical education and health of pupils and students, the importance of exercise of natural factors has an important place.

2. Comprehensive physical exercises serve as a necessary tool for refreshing the body of pupils and students and preparing them for physical exertion.

3. Special physical exercises greatly help pupils and students to acquire and improve the technique of physical movements in these types of sports.

4. Auxiliary physical exercises serve as a unique tool in the formation of special exercises of sports.

5. It is desirable to effectively use the forms of physical education, sports and wellness for pupils and students in physical education, sports and wellness events.

6. The effect of physical education, sports and wellness activities held in the heart of nature is of great importance for physical development and improvement.

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